

THE STRUCTURE OF THE MECHANISM FOR IMPLEMENTING LARGE-SCALE INNOVATION AND INVESTMENT PROJECTS OF INTEGRATIVE-COOPERATIVE ENTERPRISE PARTNERSHIPS

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Abstract

The structure of the implementation mechanism for large-scale innovation and investment projects within integrative and cooperative enterprise collaboration is substantiated, and its components are characterized. It has been proven that the necessity of accumulating significant volumes of production resources for implementing large-scale innovation and investment projects determines the expediency of establishing integrative and cooperative interactions when building global value chains. The mechanism developed by the author is considered not only in a static dimension but as a dynamic architecture that unites the interests of research structures, financial institutions, government agencies, and consumers. Key principles for forming the mechanism are defined: parity (equal access to project management), systemic nature (the interdependence of all links in cooperation), and complementarity (the mutual complementarity of partners' competencies). The role of digitalization in creating a unified information field for the project is revealed, and it is proven that algorithmization should not replace direct communication channels when making strategic decisions under conditions of uncertainty. Specific cooperation risks are identified, in particular, opportunistic behavior and the threat of losing core competencies due to excessive specialization.

Keywords: large-scale innovation and investment projects, integrative and cooperative interaction, value chains, sustainable competitive advantages, stakeholders, institutional ordering, organizational-economic mechanism.

Introduction. The economic basis for ensuring sustainable economic development and growth necessitates the implementation of large-scale innovation and investment projects. Within these projects, the extensive application of scientific and technological progress is directed toward expanding productive capacities to satisfy a wide range of consumer needs and demands. In turn, the execution of such large-scale initiatives requires the concentrated accumulation of all types of production resources, the required volumes of which typically significantly exceed the financial capabilities of any individual enterprise.

Therefore, addressing the multitude of economic tasks associated with these development projects, especially under modern conditions where cooperation is intensifying through the construction of extended (global and international) value chains, predominantly implies the expediency of establishing integrative and cooperative interaction. The driving force behind the expansion of such collaboration is an extensive system of motives and incentives, the essence and manifestation of which depend crucially on the priorities, objectives, and specific requirements for implementing large-scale innovation and investment projects.

Thus, the formation of an effective implementation mechanism for such projects must envision and account for the aforementioned multifaceted nature of this process. Within this framework, integrative and cooperative interaction serves as the fundamental basis for achieving strategic goals, not only in the context of

executing specific project operations but also in maintaining the stability and continuity of strategic partnerships. Establishing such partnerships acts as a powerful source for creating sustainable competitive advantages for participants within the respective value chain. From this perspective, the specified mechanism should outline not only the static (structural) dimension of organizing project work but also represent a dynamic architecture that integrates the interests of various stakeholder groups (research structures, enterprises, financial institutions, government agencies, end consumers, etc.).

However, it must be noted that, both in the pre-war conditions of market transformation in Ukraine's national economy and (even more so) in the current context of wartime crisis circumstances, the formalization of such a mechanism in domestic business practices has remained structurally fragmented and functionally limited. On the other hand, establishing effective integrative and cooperative collaboration among enterprises and other participants in large-scale innovation and investment projects represents an integral component and an indispensable requirement for ensuring the post-war recovery of the national economy.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Various aspects of forming the mechanism for implementing large-scale innovation and investment projects based on integrative and cooperative enterprise collaboration have been examined in detail in the works of authoritative international and Ukrainian scholars, such as Aldea A. [1], Argoneto P. [2], Corsi P. [3], Endres

H. [4] Jacob M.E. [1], Lankhorst M. [1, 5] Litvinenko A. [6], Neau E. [3], Pylypenko A. [6], Renna P. [2], Sousa P. [7], Vasconcelos A. [7], Vivek K. [8], Wunder T. [9] etc. At the same time, certain issues, particularly those related to the institutional arrangement of the structure and functional scope of the corresponding organizational-economic mechanism, remain insufficiently addressed to date and warrant further investigation.

The aim of the research in this work is to substantiate the structure and characterize the components of the implementation mechanism for large-scale innovation and investment projects within integrative and cooperative enterprise collaboration.

Research Results. The conceptual basis for the formation of the studied mechanism is determined by the integrative and cooperative nature of combining participants' contributions to the implementation of large-scale innovation and investment projects, within which the innovation foundation (creation, implementation, and commercial development of a new product or technology) is closely intertwined with the investment component, which must ensure the financial capacity for the practical embodiment of innovative solutions into business practices.

The key principles, the adherence to which will ensure the targeted nature of the orientation of integrative and cooperative enterprise collaboration regarding the implementation of large-scale innovation and investment projects during the formation of this mechanism, should be considered as follows: parity in the distribution of responsibility and authority (ensuring equal access to project management, regardless of the volume of capital contributed, which is critically important for protecting the interests of developers of innovative solutions, whose contribution to cooperation is of an intellectual nature and is not directly related to the accumulation of financial capital); systemic nature (viewing cooperation as a form of ensuring a time-extended sequence of projects, the implementation of which occurs within the formalization of a set of interconnected elements, where a change in one of the links must lead to a correction of investment plans and corresponding organizational-economic support in the context of the entire cooperation chain); complementarity (the selection of partners must be based on the mutual complementarity of competencies, where the effectiveness of interaction will decisively depend on the seamless nature of building the value-added chain).

Organizational support for the formation and functioning of the studied integration mechanism is carried out through the development of an extensive system of cooperative forms, among which the leading place is occupied by strategic alliances (allowing large players to combine efforts in risky developments while maintaining legal independence), industrial clusters (ensuring the territorial concentration of interconnected companies, which allows for minimizing logistics costs and stimulating the "diffusion of innovations" among participants), and temporary consortia (created for specific state or international tenders where a broad spectrum of qualifications is a requirement).

At the same time, the organizational component of

the specified mechanism remains the most variable part of the partnership cooperation system. Thus, the disclosure of the productive capacity of the extensive network of these cooperative forms occurs by adapting integration cooperation to the conditions of the life cycle deployment of specific innovation and investment projects. Within such a flexible structure, the integrated association forms specific management bodies responsible for coordinating actions and aligning the often-conflicting interests of participants.

The functional block of the mechanism, which covers the processes of continuous planning, monitoring of intermediate results, and operational risk management, acquires special significance. It is functional flexibility that allows the project to remain viable even under conditions of high environmental uncertainty characteristic of innovative activity. An important element in supporting the functional flexibility of integrative and cooperative collaboration is the creation of a project steering body (committee) (i.e., a supranational or supracorporate body) in which authority and responsibility for operational decision-making are concentrated. Centralization of management of this kind allows for overcoming certain obstacles (bureaucratic barriers) within individual enterprises that are participants in a specific association.

The functional component of the mechanism encompasses the processes that ensure the vitality of the cooperative interaction network, in which the knowledge management mechanism holds a central place. This type of cooperation involves the exchange of tacit knowledge (experience, know-how), which requires a high level of trust. Additionally, the functional block encompasses protocols for exchanging information and sharing scientific and technological resources (such as laboratories and test benches).

Furthermore, the specific functionality of the implementation mechanism for large-scale innovation and investment projects within integrative and cooperative collaboration is related to the processing of work on cross-functional monitoring. The importance of this type of management work is determined by the long duration of the investment phase, extending from the initial stage to the point of commercializing innovations. Within cross-functional monitoring, it is expedient to establish a system of intermediate KPIs, which combines the cost and technological aspects (accounting for the dynamics of growth in technological readiness) of cooperative interaction.

The financial and investment component of the mechanism for implementing large projects is based on the principles of multi-source (multisensory) financing, through which the combined accumulation of enterprises' own funds, attracted capital, and state support occurs within the accumulation of the capital base of integrative and cooperative interaction during the implementation of large-scale projects. An important element of establishing such cooperation within projects of (primarily) an infrastructural orientation can be public-private partnership tools and syndicated lending mechanisms, which allow for distributing capital-intensive loads and financial risks among many entities. At the same time, the investment process in the structure of the

mechanism is considered not simply as the provision of capital, but as the active management of project value at each stage of its life cycle (from the stage of research and development to commercialization and scaling of the finished product).

The implementation of an integrative and cooperative project is impossible without powerful information technology support, which in modern conditions is transformed into a digital project ecosystem. The use of digitalization technologies, in particular digital twins and product lifecycle management (PLM) systems, allows partners to work in a unified information field, ensuring process transparency and the speed of exchange of intellectual assets. At the same time, this requires clear legal regulation in the structure of the mechanism, especially in terms of protecting intellectual property rights and defining protocols for the distribution of future profits.

A separate critical aspect of the mechanism is the system for managing specific risks that arise specifically in the process of cooperation, such as information asymmetry or opportunistic behavior of partners. To neutralize them, internal audit and cross-functional control tools are integrated into the structure of the mechanism. The final element of the system is the result block, which not only records the economic efficiency of investments but also evaluates the socio-economic and technological effect for the industry as a whole. Thus, only under the condition of a harmonious combination of methodological, organizational, financial, and digital components is the mechanism for implementing large projects capable of transforming the potential for integration into a real innovation breakthrough that will ensure the long-term competitiveness of all cooperation participants.

The deployment and support of sustainable, integrative, and cooperative collaboration critically depend on the capacity to identify and account for relevant specific risks. In this regard, risk distribution, as a key form of threat optimization for the implementation of large-scale innovation and investment projects (the nature of which does not allow for the full application of other optimization methods, such as creating reserves, insurance, or risk avoidance), should be carried out within the framework of the studied mechanism based on the deepening of specialization (implying the allocation of responsibility according to the principle that "the risk is borne by the one who can manage it best").

Another critical component of risk management in this context will be the use of digital tools (such as ERP systems, cloud platforms for collaborative development), which, in modern conditions of digitalization, will facilitate the reduction of information distribution asymmetry between partners, ensure transparency in the use of investment resources, and accelerate the progression of stages in the innovation-investment cycle, etc.

On the other hand, the scaling of digitalization in management processes should not hinder the functioning of direct communication channels at the strategic (top management) and key operational (primarily engineering and technology) levels of decision-making. Within the framework of implementing large projects,

strategic decisions are often made in a zone of high uncertainty, where the limited availability of reliable primary data complicates the algorithmization of optimal decision-making.

Consequently, the emphasis of management attention in the field of information support should shift from prioritizing data storage tools to technologies for the secure exchange of intellectual assets and the protection of commercial secrets within the group.

The source of a separate group of specific risks associated with integrative and cooperative interaction may be the system of relationships among participants in innovation and investment projects. The sources of such risks include, first, possible manifestations of opportunistic behavior (an attempt by a particular participant to obtain benefits at the expense of others, for example, by hiding real costs or poaching key specialists). To mitigate this risk, cross-audit tools and mutual ownership of shares in project companies are integrated into the mechanism.

Second, due to the danger of losing core competencies through excessive specialization of certain participants within a large-scale project, the risks of compromising the integrity of the perception of cooperation conditions potentially increase. Therefore, within the framework of the organizational mechanism for implementing cooperative relations, provisions should be made for staff rotation and regular joint strategic planning sessions to maintain a holistic vision, among other measures.

Conclusions. The structural construction of the implementation mechanism for large-scale innovation and investment projects in modern conditions is consistently transforming from the foundations of a rigid vertical hierarchy to the use of a flexible, networked integration approach. The key economic resource for the formation and functioning of such a cooperative system is the capacity for coordinated action, a jointly formed set of strategic competencies that enable rebuilding an extensive cooperation network to create new value in conditions of increasing competitive rivalry intensity. Ensuring the harmony of methodological unity, organizational flexibility, and financial solidarity among participants within a holistic cooperation mechanism thus allows for transforming the local production capabilities of individual enterprises into an aggregate potential for forming a cooperative interaction chain.

Directions for further research will focus on the development of organizational, economic, and methodological support for implementing large-scale innovation and investment projects through integrative and cooperative enterprise collaboration.

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